

Beer's law and physical constants

Beer's law was valid up to 10 ppm of cobalt. The Sandell sensitivity of the reaction as calculated from Beer's plot is found to be $0.00727 \mu\text{g Co cm}^{-2}$ at 365 nm for $\log I_0/I=0.001$. The molar extinction coefficient of the complex is $8095 \text{ l mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The Ringbom's plot indicated that the optimum range is 1.6 to $5.0 \mu\text{g Co ml}^{-1}$.

Effect of pH

A series of solutions varying in pH from 3 to 12 were prepared and the absorbances were recorded at 365 nm. It was observed that no change in absorbance took place over the pH range 7 to 8. The absorbance of the solutions decreases at higher or lower pH values. The pH 7.5 was maintained in further studies.

Effect of reagent concentration

It was observed that 0.75 ml of the reagent solution is adequate for colour development. However twice the amount was used to ensure full colour development. The reagent has negligible absorbance at the wavelength selected for measurement.

Composition of the complex

Job's method of continuous variation⁸ was studied. Solutions were mixed in different proportions keeping the total molarity constant. The curve obtained indicates the formation of cobalt complex in which the metal : ligand ratio is 1 : 2. This conclusion is supported by the mole ratio⁹ and slope ratio¹⁰⁻¹¹ methods.

Effect of diverse ions

The solutions containing known amounts of cobalt and varying amounts of diverse ions were prepared and cobalt was determined in their presence. It was observed that large number of cations such as Ti^{3+} , UO_2^{2+} , Mo^{6+} , Zn^{2+} , V^{5+} , Ba^{2+} , Sr^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Re^{6+} , Ce^{2+} , Cr^{3+} , Pb^{2+} , In^{3+} can be tolerated in the ratio of at least 1 : 20. Fairly large number of anions like SO_4^{2-} , $\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$, HCO_3^- , HCOO^- , HC_2O_4^- , tartrate are tolerated in large amounts. Nickel ion shows strong interference and must be absent. Interference of copper can be avoided by prior separation¹². Fluoride ion can be used as masking agent for Mn(II) and Fe(III) up to 30 ppm.

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Oxazine Dyes as New Iodometric Indicators[†]

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IN a continuation of our work on the use of oxazine dyes as indicators¹⁻⁴, we have found that eight oxazine dyes, Capri Blue(CPB), Meldola's Blue (MB), Celestine Blue(CLB), Gallamine Blue(GB), Solochrome Prune AS(SPAS), Brilliant Cresyl Blue (BCB) (Colour Index Nos. 51015, 51175, 51050, 51045, 51040 and 51010 respectively), Cresyl Fast Violet Acetate(CFVA), and Resazurin(RSZ) (the structures of these dyes are given below), can be used as indicators in the direct and reverse titrations of iodine with thiosulphate, arsenic(III), ascorbic acid, hydrazine, mercaptoacetic acid and uric acid. The advantages of these indicators are : their solubility in cold water and stability of their aqueous solutions. In this connection, it may be mentioned that till now very few indicators have been reported for the titration of ascorbic acid⁵⁻⁸ and hydrazine⁹ with iodine, and apart from starch, no other indicator has been proposed for the uric acid-iodine titration⁹.

The indicator methods now developed have been utilised for the determination of ascorbic acid content of commercial vitamin C tablets and some fruit

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juices, as well as the determination of uric acid content of human urine,

Experimental

0.1N solutions of iodine (in 2% KI solution), sodium thiosulphate, hydrazine sulphate, mercaptoacetic acid, ascorbic acid (EDTA was used as stabiliser) and 0.025N uric acid (1 g of uric acid + 0.7 g of lithium carbonate in 500 ml water) were prepared and standardised. 0.1N arsenic(III) solution was also prepared.

the solution with 0.1N (or 0.01N) sodium thiosulphate solution. The colour changes at the end points are : green to blue with CPB and BCB, light pink to violet with MB and CFVA, orange-red to pink with CLB, GB and SPAS and green to violet (orange-red to pink in titrations with ascorbic acid and mercaptoacetic acid) with RSZ.

The same procedure can be employed using arsenic(III), ascorbic acid, hydrazine sulphate, mercaptoacetic acid or uric acid in place of sodium thiosulphate, provided, 0.5-1.0 g of sodium bicarbonate is added to the titration mixture while titrating

Capri Blue
(Colour Index No. 51015)

Meldola's Blue
(Colour Index No. 51175)

Celestine Blue
(Colour Index No. 51050)

Gallamine Blue
(Colour Index No. 51045)

Soleochrome Prune As
(Colour Index No. 51040)

Brilliant Cresyl Blue
(Colour Index No. 51010)

Cresyl Fast Violet Acetate

Resazurin

0.1% solutions (0.2% in the case of GB) of the dyes were prepared from the following dye samples : CPB, MB, SPAS and CFVA : Gurr ; CLB and GB : Chroma ; BCB : E. Merck ; RSZ : Baird & Tatlock (London) Ltd.

General Procedure : Transfer 3-10 ml of 0.1N (or 0.01N) iodine solution (0.025N in the case of titrations with uric acid) into a 250 ml iodine flask, dilute to 50 ml and add 0.1 ml of 0.1% CPB, MB, or BCB or 0.2 ml of 0.1% CLB, SPAS or CFVA or 0.2 ml of 0.2% GB or 0.05 ml of 0.1% RSZ, and titrate

with arsenic(III) and hydrazine sulphate solutions. Titrations with uric acid have to be conducted in presence of 2-3 g of sodium bicarbonate.

The results obtained by this method are in excellent agreement with those obtained by other methods.

Results and Discussion

Mechanism of indicator action : While discussing the use of Neutral Red, an azine dye, as indicator in the titration of iodide with silver nitrate, Sierra

and Asensi Mora¹⁰ have stated that the colour change at the end point was due to the formation of a compound between Neutral Red and iodine. Since the eight dyes of the present investigation are very closely related to Neutral Red, we believe that a similar mechanism is operative in the iodometric titrations now reported. That is, a compound is formed between the dye and iodine and at the end point, thiosulphate, arsenic(III), etc., react with the compound and regenerate the dye. In this connection, it may be mentioned that Gautier¹¹ has proposed a similar mechanism in his studies on the use of the thiazine dye, Methylene Blue, as an iodometric indicator and spot test reagent for the detection of arsenic(III), thiosulphate, etc.

Determination of ascorbic acid content in commercial vitamin C tablets and fruit juices : Substances like maltose, lactose, dextrose, citric acid, tartaric acid, succinic acid, maleic acid, malic acid and mandelic acid do not interfere in the iodometric titration of ascorbic acid using the present oxazine dye indicators. Consequently, the determination of ascorbic acid content in commercial vitamin C tablets is carried out in accordance with the method of Rao and Prasad⁹ employing 0.025N iodine solution and any one of the afore-mentioned dyes as indicator. The data presented in Table 1 show that the results obtained by the present indicator method are in excellent agreement with those obtained by the B.P. method¹².

TABLE—1 ESTIMATION OF ASCORBIC ACID IN COMMERCIAL VITAMIN C TABLETS

Trade name & manufacturer	Ascorbic acid found, mg	
	B.P. method	Present method
Sucksee, IDPL	530 ± 2	533 ± 2
Redoxon, Roche	505 ± 2	508 ± 2
Celin, Glaxo	485 ± 2	487 ± 2
Chewsee, Lederle	511 ± 2	513 ± 2

Attempts for the estimation of ascorbic acid content of some fruit juices yielded satisfactory results with only Capri Blue and Brilliant Cresyl Blue as indicators ; with other indicators, the colour changes at the end points are not sharp. The results obtained with Capri Blue and Brilliant Cresyl Blue as indicators are in very good agreement with those obtained adopting the method given by Jacobs¹³ as is evident from Table 2.

In these titrations, 0.025N iodine solution should be used as titrant and the titration should be carried out rapidly, as otherwise, the results obtained will not be accurate.

Determination of uric acid in human urine : The iodometric method for the determination of uric acid, using the indicators now proposed, can be applied for the determination of uric acid in human urine. The uric acid in the urine is precipitated as the ammonium salt, the ammonium salt dissolved

TABLE—2 ESTIMATION OF ASCORBIC ACID CONTENT OF SOME FRUIT JUICES

Fruit		Ascorbic acid in 100 ml of juice, mg	
Common name	Botanical name	Jacob's method	Present method
Tomato	<i>Lycopersicum esculentum</i>	35.6 ± 0.2	36.1 ± 0.3
Lemon	<i>C. aurantifolia</i> (christm)	29.5 ± 0.2	30.4 ± 0.3
Orange	<i>C. aurantium</i> L.	46.2 ± 0.2	46.6 ± 0.3
Batavia	<i>C. sinensis</i> (L) Osbeck	95.9 ± 0.3	95.9 ± 0.3
Grape	<i>Vitis vinifera</i>	12.3 ± 0.2	12.2 ± 0.3

in the minimum amount of 10% acetic acid and the resulting solution is titrated with iodine using the oxazine dye indicators, after adding 2 ml of saturated sodium bicarbonate solution. The results obtained are incorporated in Table 3.

TABLE—3 ESTIMATION OF URIC ACID IN HUMAN URINE

Sample No.	Volume of urine, ml	Uric acid, mg	
		Danet's method ¹⁴	Present method
1	10.0	4.9 ± 0.1	4.9 ± 0.1
2	10.0	4.0 ± 0.1	4.0 ± 0.1
3	10.0	4.5 ± 0.1	4.5 ± 0.1
4	10.0	4.2 ± 0.1	4.2 ± 0.1

Reverse titrations : The reverse titrations, i.e., titrations of sodium thiosulphate, arsenic(III), ascorbic acid, hydrazine, mercaptoacetic acid and uric acid, with iodine, can be performed in 0.1N and 0.01N solutions, using the eight oxazine dyes as indicators, under the same conditions of direct titrations. The colour changes at the end points are just the reverse of those obtained in the direct titrations. In titrations of 0.1N solutions, no blank correction is necessary but while employing 0.01N solutions, the following blank corrections (of 0.01N iodine solution) should be applied : CPB and BCB : 0.02 ml ; MB and RSZ : 0.08 ml ; CLB, GB and SPAS : 0.04 ml. The colour change with CFVA is not satisfactory.

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0.2 ml. (4 drops) of 1% indicator solution. It was then titrated against 0.05M acidic ferric chloride of pH 1.5 at room temperature. The end point is marked with a sharp change of yellow to red colour.

It was found that the presence of 50 times excess of Cl^- , Br^- , NO_3^- and SO_4^{2-} was tolerated in this estimation of the fluoride.

It is evident from the results that the fluoride can be determined satisfactorily by the use of 5-alkoxy-2-nitroso phenols as indicators, even when the fluoride content is very low. These compounds are found to be efficient indicators because they form less strong complexes with ferric(III) rather than iron fluoride complex.

New Indicators for Titrimetric Determination of Fluoride by Ferric Chloride

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THIOCYANATE¹, sodium salicylate² and resacetophenone oxime³ have been investigated as indicators for the titrimetric determination of fluoride. Many other indicators like alizarin red⁴, methyl thymol blue⁵, xylenol orange⁶, Na-rhodizonate⁷, Na-purpurin-3-sulphonate⁸ have been tried for its volumetric estimation. Even 4(2-pyridylazo) resorcinol has been studied for its titrimetric determination by various workers⁹⁻¹⁰. 5-alkoxy-2-nitroso-phenols have been prepared^{11,12} in the laboratory and used as chelating agents for bivalent metal ions. This article reports the use of these compounds as indicators for the titrimetric determination of fluoride with acidic ferric chloride solution.

Experimental

A stock solution of 0.1M sodium fluoride was prepared by dissolving 2.1 g of NaF in 500 ml of distilled water. 0.05M ferric chloride solution was prepared by dissolving 6.7575 g of ferric chloride hexahydrate in 500 ml of 0.01M HCl, 1% solutions of the pure samples of 5-methoxy-2-nitroso phenol, 5-ethoxy-2-nitroso phenol and 5-propoxy-2-nitroso phenol were prepared by dissolving required quantity in 95% ethanol. These solutions are fairly stable and give yellow colour with fluoride ion and very low concentration is required for the titration.

An aliquot of sodium fluoride solution was taken in a 100 ml conical flask. About 2.0 g of NaCl was added to it. The contents were shaken thoroughly well and then equal volume of 95% ethanol was added to it, which was followed by the addition of

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The Influence of Different Frequencies of Laser on the Microbial Production of Alcohol by *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*

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THE applications of laser to study of biological system have been reviewed by many workers¹⁻³. Both stimulating^{4,5} and inhibitory⁶⁻⁸ effects of laser on living organisms particularly on enzyme systems have been found. Combined effects of laser and some chemicals on living cells have also been explored^{9,10}. But a little or no work to study the effect of laser on the fermentations has been done as yet.

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